

Table continued.

Treatment		1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
Kharif	Rabi							
NPK in the ratio 67.5:33.75:33.75 kg ha ⁻¹ through fertilizers + 22.5 kg N ha ⁻¹ through green manuring	NPK in the ratio 67.5:33.75:33.75 kg ha ⁻¹ through fertilizers	8.3	5.9	6.2	5.9	7.5	6.2	7.3
Farmers' practice (NPK in the ratio 90:22.5:45 kg ha ⁻¹ through fertilizers; no organic manure)	Same as in kharif	7.4	4.6	5.3	6.0	6.9	6.0	6.3
CD (0.05)		0.7	0.6	0.6	0.7	1.0	0.8	0.8

Transplanting geometry improves timing of uptake of deep point-placed P by rice hills

N. K. Savant, R. G. Menon, and D. K. Friesen, International Fertilizer Development Center, Muscle Shoals, Alabama 35662, USA

This greenhouse experiment tested the hypothesis that establishing a shorter distance between deep point-placed water-soluble phosphorus (P) and transplanted rice hills may help rice plant roots to intercept and recover fertilizer Pearlrier. Urea briquettes (UB) containing diammonium phosphate tagged with ³²P (UB-DAP) were deep-placed after transplanting rice (Fig. 1).

The soil used was Typic Ustochrept (pH 8.2; organic matter, 11 g kg⁻¹; CEC, 37 cmol kg⁻¹; and Olsen P, 11 mg kg⁻¹). The soil was flooded with water for 2 wk and then puddled prior to transplanting. Nitrogen and P were applied at 58 kg N ha⁻¹ and 12 kg P ha⁻¹. Estimated distances between the deep point-placed ³²P and the rice hills were about 14.1 and 10.6 cm for regular and modified spacing. As a standard for comparison, ³²P-tagged triple superphosphate (TSP) with a specific activity 74 MBq ³²P g⁻¹ P was broadcast and incorporated before transplanting, and N was applied as prilled urea in two splits

(two-thirds basally broadcast and incorporated before transplanting, and one-third topdressed at the panicle initiation stage). Four hills with two 3-wk-old-rice (IR36) seedlings hill⁻¹ were transplanted in each box and treatments were replicated three times under continuously flooded soil conditions. ■

1. Schematic sketches of regular and modified 20- x 20-cm spacings (with 25 hills m⁻²) used in the boxes.

Fertilizer P was calculated from ³²P activity in 7-ml aliquots of floodwater whose volume was estimated from its depth (measured before sampling) and surface area of soil in a box. Interception and absorption of ³²P from basally applied TSP and deep-placed UB-DAP were determined in situ by monitoring ³²P activity on a well-shielded 1-cm² area of the youngest fully developed leaf.

The results suggest that basally broadcast and incorporated soluble P fertilizers are prone to surface runoff losses under rainfed, lowland field conditions. Other experiments show practically no ³²P in the floodwater when UB-DAP is deep-placed. For the incorporated TSP, P uptake reached near-plateau 15 d after transplanting (DT) (Fig. 2). For the deep point-placed Pin regular spacing, radioactivity in the youngest leaves was not detected until about 30 and 20 DT. Thus P diffusion alone is not sufficient for onset of its uptake by rice roots. On the other hand, the onset of P uptake in the youngest leaves was observed about 10 d earlier for the modified spacing (Fig. 2). These and other results suggest that modified spacing can reduce the lag period of spatial nonavailability of deep-placed UB-DAP and help to explain improved agronomic performance reported in rainfed transplanted rice on farmers' fields. ■

2. In situ ³²P activity in youngest leaves of transplanted rice (IR36) as influenced by basal incorporation of triple superphosphate (TSP) and deep placement of urea briquettes containing diammonium phosphate (UB-DAP) in regular (R) and modified (M) 20- x 20-cm spacings.